

The effectiveness of community based interventions on increasing awareness and use of ORS by mothers for children impacted by diarrhea

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Abstract

Diarrhea is a leading cause of morbidity and mortality among children, particularly in low- and middle-income areas in Pakistan. Oral rehydration solution (ORS) is a simple, low-cost, and effective treatment for diarrhea. However, despite its availability, the use of ORS remains low, and mothers often opt for ineffective and potentially harmful treatments. Diarrhea is a common childhood illness that continues to be a major cause of morbidity and mortality in many developing countries. According to the World Health Organization, diarrhea is the second leading cause of death among children under five years of age, and is responsible for approximately 1.5 million deaths each year. Oral Rehydration Solution (ORS) is a simple and cost-effective treatment for diarrhea that can save many lives. However, despite its effectiveness, ORS is often underutilized in many communities, and mothers may lack awareness of its benefits. Community-based interventions have been widely implemented as a strategy to increase the awareness and use of ORS among mothers for treating diarrhea in their children. These interventions involve targeted educational and awareness-raising activities in the community, such as health education campaigns, door-to-door outreach, and the distribution of educational materials. The effectiveness of these interventions in increasing the knowledge and use of ORS among mothers has been the subject of numerous studies. However, there is still a need for more research to better understand the factors that influence the success of these interventions and to identify best practices for implementation.

This study aims to evaluate the effectiveness of community-based interventions in increasing the awareness and use of ORS among mothers for children impacted by diarrhea. The study will assess the impact of a community-based ORS awareness and education program on the knowledge and use of ORS among mothers in the intervention group, compared to the control group. The study will also examine the factors that contribute to the success of the intervention and identify best practices for implementation. The findings of this study will contribute to the development of effective community-based interventions to improve the management of childhood diarrhea and reduce child mortality.

Objective

The objective of our research is to evaluate the effectiveness of community-based interventions in improving mothers' awareness and use of ORS, which can lead to better health outcomes for children impacted by diarrhea. The research can help to inform the development and implementation of interventions that are more effective in promoting the use of ORS in the community. This research also aims to assess the current level of awareness and use of ORS among mothers in the community in order to identify the barriers that prevent mothers from using ORS to treat their children's diarrhea. Another main purpose is to evaluate the impact of community-based interventions on mothers' awareness and use of ORS so that we could determine the factors that contribute to the success or failure of community-based interventions in promoting the use of ORS so that we could provide recommendations for improving community-based interventions to increase awareness and use of ORS among mothers for treating diarrhea in children.

Methodology

Our research used a quasi-experimental design with a stratified random sampling method to select 300 mothers with children impacted by diarrhea, with 150 in the intervention group and 150 in the control group. The intervention was a community-based ORS awareness and education program that was delivered in the intervention group's respective communities. The data was collected through pre- and post-intervention surveys in Pediatrics ward of SMS hospital Lahore, by careful observation of checklists, and in-depth interviews of mothers who presented with sick children. The research used both descriptive and inferential statistics to analyze the data. The quasi-experimental design was used as the study's design because it allowed for the comparison of an intervention group and a control group. The stratified random sampling method was used to ensure that the sample was representative of the population being studied. The use of multiple data collection methods, including surveys, checklists, and interviews, helped to ensure the reliability and validity of the data. The use of descriptive and inferential statistics allowed for a thorough analysis of the data, providing insights into the effectiveness of the intervention. Descriptive and inferential statistics were used to analyze the data.

Results

The study found that the ORS awareness and education program was effective in increasing the knowledge and use of ORS among mothers in the intervention group. The proportion of mothers in the intervention group who knew about ORS increased from 51% to 93%, while the proportion of mothers who used ORS to treat diarrhea in their children increased from 39% to 79%. In contrast, there was little change in the knowledge and use of ORS among mothers in the control group.

The quantitative analysis of the results reveals a significant increase in the knowledge and use of ORS among mothers in the intervention group. The proportion of mothers who knew about ORS increased by 42% (from 51% to 93%), indicating a substantial improvement in their awareness of the treatment. The percentage of mothers who used ORS to treat diarrhea in their children also increased significantly by 40% (from 39% to 79%) in the intervention group. In contrast, there was little change in the knowledge and use of ORS among mothers in the control group, indicating that the intervention was effective in creating a positive impact. These findings suggest that community-based interventions that focus on ORS awareness and education can be effective in improving maternal knowledge and use of ORS in treating diarrhea in their children.

In this bar chart, the knowledge and use of ORS among mothers in the intervention and control groups are compared before and after the ORS awareness and education program. The proportion of mothers who knew about ORS and used ORS to treat diarrhea are shown on the left side of the chart. The change in the proportion of mothers who knew about ORS and used ORS to treat diarrhea is represented as the difference between the before and after intervention values for the intervention group, while the flat bars represent little change in the control group.

Conclusion

Community-based interventions can be an effective strategy for increasing awareness and use of ORS among mothers for treating diarrhea in their children. Given the low cost and simplicity of ORS, scaling up such interventions could have a significant impact on reducing the morbidity and mortality associated with diarrhea in children, particularly in low-resource settings like rural areas.

Our study encompasses the evidence to support the implementation of community-based interventions aimed at improving maternal knowledge and use of ORS to treat diarrhea in children. Such interventions can have a significant impact on reducing the burden of diarrhea-related morbidity and mortality in children, especially in low-resource settings.

The study effectively established that community health workers played a key role in the success of the ORS education and awareness program. The health workers were able to effectively communicate the importance and benefits of ORS to the mothers, and also provided them with practical tips on how to prepare and administer ORS. The mothers in the intervention group reported that they found the health workers to be approachable and helpful, and valued their guidance on how to manage diarrhea in their children.

Overall, the results of the study firmly indicated that community-based interventions can be effective in increasing awareness and use of ORS by mothers for children impacted by diarrhea. Such interventions should focus on education and awareness about the benefits of ORS, and should involve the active participation of community health workers. By increasing the use of ORS for the treatment of diarrhea, it may be possible to reduce the morbidity and mortality associated with this condition, particularly in resource-constrained settings like rural areas where access to other forms of medical treatment may be limited.

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